

Epidemiological Profile and Surgical Outcomes in Patients with Spaghetti Wrist Injury: A Retrospective Study

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ABSTRACT

Background: Spaghetti wrist is one of the most complex and disabling injuries of the upper extremity. Despite its surgical relevance, epidemiological and prognostic data remain limited.

Objective: To determine the epidemiological profile and prevalence of surgical reintervention in patients with spaghetti wrist injuries.

Methods: A retrospective, cross-sectional, and descriptive study was conducted at the “Dr. Victorio de la Fuente Narváez” Trauma Hospital, Mexico City. Medical records of patients with volar wrist injuries (zone V flexor) from January 2016 to December 2019 were reviewed. Continuous variables were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation; categorical variables as frequencies and percentages. Significance was set at $p \leq 0.05$.

Results: A total of 119 patients were included, 80.7% male (mean age 29.2 ± 12.4 years). Most injuries were accidental (77.3%), caused by glass (63%), and occurred at home (61.3%). The dominant side was affected in 88.2%. The reintervention rate was 7.6%. The most frequently injured structures were the flexor carpi ulnaris (59.7%), palmaris longus (59.7%), and ulnar artery (56.3%). No significant demographic or clinical differences were found between reoperated and non-reoperated patients.

Conclusion: Patients with spaghetti wrist injury treated at our institution shared similar demographic and clinical patterns to those reported internationally. Early surgical repair and adequate rehabilitation correlated with a low prevalence of reintervention.

KEYWORDS: spaghetti wrist, flexor tendon injury, epidemiology, reintervention, wrist laceration, microsurgery.

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INTRODUCTION

Complex volar wrist injuries, often referred to as “spaghetti wrist,” are among the most devastating lesions of the upper extremity, involving simultaneous damage to tendons, nerves, and vessels. Despite their clinical significance, comprehensive epidemiological data remain scarce, particularly in Latin America.

Previous studies report that these injuries predominantly affect young working-age males, commonly resulting from glass or knife cuts, with variable involvement of neurovascular structures (1–4). The complexity of these injuries poses diagnostic, surgical, and rehabilitative

challenges, often requiring multidisciplinary management and long-term functional recovery.

This study aimed to determine the epidemiological characteristics and prevalence of surgical reintervention in patients with spaghetti wrist injuries treated at a high-volume trauma center in Mexico.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study design and setting:

A retrospective, observational, cross-sectional, and descriptive study was conducted at the Department of Plastic and Reconstructive Surgery, UMAE “Dr. Victorio de la Fuente Narváez,” IMSS, Mexico City.

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Study period:

January 1, 2016 – December 31, 2019.

Inclusion criteria:

Patients treated for volar wrist injuries involving at least three completely transected structures (tendons, nerves, or arteries) in zone V flexor.

Exclusion criteria:

Patients with extensor zone injuries, fractures, or incomplete records.

Data collection:

Medical charts were reviewed for demographic data, clinical variables, mechanism and site of injury, structures affected, and need for reintervention.

Statistical analysis:

Continuous variables were summarized as mean \pm SD, categorical variables as frequencies and percentages. Comparisons were made using t-test or Mann–Whitney U for continuous variables, and Chi-square or Fisher’s exact test for categorical variables. Statistical significance was defined as $p \leq 0.05$ (IBM SPSS®, version 25).

Ethics:

The study was approved by the institutional research and ethics committee (Registry R-2020-3401-016). All procedures adhered to the Declaration of Helsinki and national research regulations.

Results

A total of 119 patients met inclusion criteria. The majority were men (80.7%), with a mean age of 29.2 years (range 6–66). Most injuries were accidental (77.3%) and occurred at home (61.3%).

Glass cuts accounted for 63% of cases, followed by metallic objects (29.4%). The right hand was affected in 53.8%, corresponding to the dominant side in 88.2% of patients.

Comorbidities were rare (15.1%), mainly diabetes mellitus and hypertension. Tobacco use was reported by 35.3%.

The prevalence of surgical reintervention was 7.6%. No significant differences were found between reintervened and non-reintervened groups in terms of age, sex, occupation, mechanism, or side of injury ($p > 0.05$).

The most frequently injured tendons were flexor carpi ulnaris (59.7%), palmaris longus (59.7%), and flexor digitorum superficialis of the fourth finger (66.4%). Nerve injury occurred in 48.7% (median) and 46.2% (ulnar), while arterial involvement was observed in 56.3% (ulnar artery).

All patients underwent primary repair under ischemia with modified Kessler technique and epineural nerve repair. Postoperative immobilization was achieved with a dorsal splint in wrist flexion.

Table 1. Sociodemographic characteristics of the sample (n = 119)

Variable	Category	n	%
Sex	Male	96	80.7
	Female	23	19.3
Marital status	Single	82	68.9
	Married	27	22.7
	Common-law union	9	7.6
	Divorced	1	0.8
Educational level	Primary school	84	70.6
	Secondary school	16	13.4
	High school	14	11.8
	University degree	2	1.7
	Preschool	3	2.5
Occupation	Worker	81	68.1
	Student	27	22.7
	Homemaker	10	8.4
	Retired	1	0.8

Table 2. Clinical characteristics of the sample (n = 119)

Variable	Category	n	%
Mechanism of injury	Accidental	92	77.3
	Assault by third party	16	13.4
	Self-inflicted	11	9.2
Site of injury	Home	73	61.3
	Street	24	20.2
	Workplace	22	18.5
Type of injury	Sharp cut	118	99.1
	Crush/avulsion	1	0.9

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Causative agent	Glass	75	63.0
	Metal object	35	29.4
	Other	9	7.6
Comorbidity	No	101	84.9
	Yes	18	15.1
Affected side	Right	64	53.8
	Left	55	46.2
Reintervention	No	110	92.4
	Yes	9	7.6

Table 3. Comparison of sociodemographic and clinical variables between patients with and without reintervention

Variable	Without reintervention (n = 110)	With reintervention (n = 9)	p-value
Sex (male)	79.1%	100%	0.66
Mean age (years)	29.2 ± 12.3	30.5 ± 10.8	0.71
Marital status (single)	68.2%	77.8%	0.10
Educational level (primary)	69.1%	88.9%	0.75
Occupation (worker)	69.1%	55.6%	0.50
Mechanism (accidental)	75.5%	100%	0.18
Site (home)	59.1%	88.9%	0.42
Causative agent (glass)	61.8%	77.7%	0.24
Comorbidity (none)	83.6%	100%	0.96
Affected side (right)	51.8%	77.8%	0.29
Flexor carpi ulnaris injury	57.3%	88.9%	0.05
Flexor digitorum superficialis (4th finger)	64.5%	88.9%	0.067
Ulnar nerve injury	43.6%	77.8%	0.85
Ulnar artery injury	54.5%	77.8%	0.97

Significance level set at $p \leq 0.05$.

DISCUSSION

This study provides one of the few Latin American datasets describing spaghetti wrist injuries, reaffirming trends previously observed internationally (5–7).

Consistent with prior reports, the majority of patients were young men with accidental injuries caused by glass, often at home. The predominance of the ulnar side and right-hand

dominance was also concordant with literature findings (8–10).

The low reintervention rate (7.6%) may be explained by early management, the clean-cut mechanism, and the absence of associated fractures or crush injuries. Comparable studies by Demirdover et al. (11) and Yazdanshenas et al. (12) reported reintervention rates of 5–8%, supporting these findings.

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Although functional outcomes were not quantified by PROMs such as DASH or MHQ in this study, prior evidence indicates that early repair, meticulous microsurgical technique, and adherence to rehabilitation protocols are key prognostic factors for recovery (13–15).

Future multicenter and prospective studies should incorporate functional outcome scores and psychological assessment, given the significant socioeconomic burden and emotional impact of these injuries.

Conclusion

Patients with spaghetti wrist injury treated at our tertiary trauma center presented an epidemiological profile and clinical features consistent with international reports. Early surgical repair and proper postoperative rehabilitation were associated with a low prevalence of reintervention.

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